

Identification of odour-active trace compounds in toasted oak wood: impact on wines and spirits aroma

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Abstract

The aging of wine in oak barrels is an important step in the maturation of quality wines. The oak toasting process generates several nuances that can be released into the wine. Significant research has been devoted to identifying the wood-derived volatile compounds that influence wine aromas [1, 2] (e.g., whisky-lactone, maltol, eugenol, guaiacol, vanillin). However, these compounds only partially explain oak wood aromas and their effect on wine complexity. The purpose of our research was to gain a greater understanding of toasted oak aromas. To achieve this, we used a sensory-guided approach based on the purification of organic extracts of crude oak wood using a preparative high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) technique and gas chromatography analysis paired with olfactometry and high-resolution mass spectrometry (GC-O-TOF MS). This approach revealed odorous zones in oak wood extracts with reminiscence of metal and pastry aromas. The odorous zone with metallic aroma was attributed to (*E*)-4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-decenal, while the one with pastry aroma was attributed to 2,4,6-nonatrienal isomers. The injection of standard confirmed the identification of (*E*)-4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-decenal. Two isomers were detected for the 2,4,6-nonatrienal compound (E,E,Z and E,E,E). We used a chemical organic synthesis method (Wittig reaction) to synthesize the isomers. An additional purification step using semi-preparative HPLC allowed us to isolate the (E,E,Z) isomer with 99% purity. These compounds were identified for the first time in wood, wine and spirits by using SPE extraction and optimized GC-MS NCI (NH₃) separation and detection. Furthermore, their very low olfactory-detection threshold in a hydro-alcoholic model solution demonstrated their impact on the aroma of these beverages. Their quantitation in numerous samples of oak wood also revealed the influence of toasting intensity on their formation. Additional results on their precursors in oak and wine were also discussed.

Keywords: toasted oak wood, (*E*)-4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-decenal, 2,4,6-nonatrienal, sensory impact, chemical synthesis

Introduction

Oak barrel aging has been recognized as an important step in the production of quality wines and spirits. Among the 250 species of the genus *Quercus*, empirical selection by wine industry professionals in recent oenological history has revealed that only three species produce quality wood suitable for oenological use: two European oak species, sessile oak (*Quercus sessilis* or *petrae*) and pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur*), and an American oak species called white oak (*Quercus alba*). Oak barrel production involves many steps, including the important toasting process. The wood is first subjected to high temperatures (160 °C - 210 °C) to facilitate bending. Heat is then applied a second time to produce a variety of volatile compounds through the thermal-degradation of oak wood components. The second heating is called oenological heating or *bousinage*. Coopers possess the expertise needed to carry out this process, which is the source of a true olfactory fingerprint. When oak wood is subjected to toasting, its odour changes. Its aromas can be reminiscent of a mix of coconut, vanilla and pastry aromas in the case of light to medium heating and produce aromas reminiscent of toasted bread, roasting, spices and even smoke aromas when heated to the highest temperatures.

Over the last 30 years, many studies have been conducted to characterize these aromas. A literature review allowed us to list around 350 volatile compounds in oak wood. These compounds belong to different chemical families, including alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, carboxylic acids, esters and lactones. The organoleptic impact has only been identified for certain compounds. For example, the two isomers of β-methyl-γ-octalactone (whisky lactone, [1]) with coconut notes, vanillin with vanilla odours [3], the Maillard derivative compounds as maltol, furfural, 5-methylfurfural with caramel notes [4, 5], and eugenol, isoeugenol, guaiacol and its derivatives with spicy aromas, leather and smoky notes [1, 6]. These compounds are produced by the thermal-degradation of the three main components of oak wood: cellulose (40-50 %), hemicellulose (28 %) and lignin (16-25 %). On the other hand, toasting can lead to volatile compound degradation, such as *trans*-2-nonenal, which is associated with a sawdust odour [7]. Therefore, although many oak wood-derived volatile compounds had been identified and studied in toasted oak wood, there was a need to identify others in order to enrich our understanding of oak wood quality for oenological use. For example, certain aromas observed in wine and wood, such as pastry, roasted and

smoky notes, had not yet been explained from a molecular standpoint. The goal of this study was to identify the volatile compounds associated with these aromas in toasted oak wood.

Experimental Methods

Samples of oak wood, wine and spirits

For the identification work, oak wood samples (*Q. sessilis*) were provided by Seguin Moreau cooperage (Merpins, France). During this first step, three commercial samples were selected with different aromas and toasting intensities, referred to respectively as vanilla, toasted and smoked. As its name suggests, the first sample was reminiscent of vanilla. The second had a complex mixture of toasted bread, pastry, and coconut aromas. The third had smoke aromas. The cooper performed additional toasting experiments involving different time and temperature combinations. Several species were selected for use in the quantitation experiments, including sessile, pedunculate, American, Caucase, chestnut, acacia and cherry wood species.

In addition, the wines (red and white) and spirits (Cognac, whisky, rum, brandy) studied were produced using different grape varieties and winemaking or aging processes. They were either supplied by winemakers, Seguin Moreau cooperage, or purchased from stores.

Sample preparation and GC-O-TOF MS experiments

GC-O-MS analysis was performed on organic extracts of oak wood solution (50 g/L, EtOH 12%, 7 days), obtained from three successive liquid-liquid extractions (100 mL of oak wood solution, 3x5 mL of dichloromethane). In order to purify the matrix and target the odorous zones (OZ), a semi-preparative HPLC fractionation was performed on these organic extracts. Reversed-phase (RP) HPLC was performed on the raw organic extract, using a Novapak C18 column (300 × 7.8 mm internal diameter (i.d.), 6 μm, Waters, Saint Quentin, France) with a guard column of the same phase. The Ultimate 3000 semi-preparative HPLC system was from Dionex (Courtaboeuf, France). The chromatographic conditions were as follows: flow rate, 1 mL/min; injection volume, 250 μL; eluent A, microfiltered water, eluent B, ethanol; gradient, 0–2 min, 0% B, 2–50 min, 0–100% B. Fifty effluent fractions of 1 mL were collected. Each fraction was diluted into 12% ethanol, then poured into normalized glasses for sensory evaluation by a panel of four experts who were asked to describe them. Among fractions, some were selected as fractions of interest based on their sensory descriptors. These selected fractions were extracted by liquid-liquid extraction (same protocol) and then injected into an Agilent 7890A gas chromatograph (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA) on a BP20 capillary column (50 m x 0.22 mm (i.d.), 0.25 μm, SGE) and a DB5 capillary column (50 m x 0.22 mm (i.d.), 0.25 μm, Agilent) coupled to an ODP-3 olfactometric port (Gerstel, Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany) and a JMS-T100GC time-of-flight mass spectrometer (JEOL Ltd, Akishima, Tokyo, Japan).

Synthesis and purification of 2,4,6-nonatrienal isomers

Inspired by the work of Schuh and Schieberle [8], the organic synthesis of (*E,E,Z*)-2,4,6-nonatrienal was optimized. This involves adding double bonds to (*Z*)-2-penten-1-ol via a Wittig reaction, while avoiding isomerization during the six steps required to add three conjugated double bonds in the molecule. Next, a semi-preparative HPLC purification using a ChiralPak IA column (25 cm, 1 cm (i.d.), 5 μm particle size, Chiral Technologies Inc., West Chester, PA, USA) was performed to isolate and characterize each synthesized isomer by ¹H NMR (300 MHz).

Development and validation of a quantitative method

A quantitative method using solid-phase extraction (SPE) was developed and validated to quantify 2,4,6-nonatrienal isomers and (*E*)-4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-decenal in oak wood, wines and spirits. Quantitation was performed on a Trace GC Ultra system coupled to a mass spectrometer DSQ II (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) using negative chemical ionization with ammonia (NCI).

*Organoleptic impact of (*E,E,Z*) 2,4,6-nonatrienal and (*E*)-4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-decenal*

Olfactory detection thresholds (ODT) were evaluated according to the ISO standard (ISO 13301:2018) in a model wine solution (ethanol 12 % vol., L(+)-tartaric acid 5g/L, pH 3.5). In order to confirm the sensory impact of the volatile compounds, concentrations were compared to ODT (ratio concentration/ODT). If the ratio was above 1, we could conclude that the compound had a direct sensory impact.

Results and discussion

Identification of the volatile compounds responsible for toasted oak wood aromas by GC-O-TOFMS

The first step in this process was the comparison of aromagrams of oak wood extracts, with differentiated aromas, obtained by GC-O-MS analysis. The aromagrams revealed the complexity of these samples, in which more than 60 OZ were detected. Comparison of aromagrams from the three commercial oak samples showed three intense and unknown OZ, specific to one particular toasting intensity and sensory profile: two with pastry odours (LRI 1839 and 1928, OZ1 and OZ1') and the other with a metallic odour (LRI 1932, OZ2) (Table 1).

Table 1: Example of aromagram illustrating odorous zones detected and identified by GC-O-TOF MS analysis of three toasted oak wood extracts (Vanilla, Toasted and Smoked).

LRI ¹	Odorous zone	Identified compound	Vanilla	Toasted	Smoked
1822	apple sauce	β -damascenone	+	+	+
1839	puff pastry	unknown	+	+	-
1847	coconut	(Z)-whisky lactone	+	+	+
1861	caramel	cyclotene	-	+	-
1868	wine vinegar, acid	unknown	+	+	+
1875	coconut	γ -octalactone	+	-	-
1894	curry, sweet	unknown	+	+	+
1906	vanilla, almond, chocolate, sweet, prune	unknown	+	+	+
1913	coconut	(E)-whisky lactone	+	+	+
1917	caramel, cooked strawberry	maltol	+	+	+
1928	puff pastry	unknown	+	+	-
1932	metallic, fatty	unknown	-	+	+

¹Linear retention indices on BP20 (50 m; 0.22 mm, 0.25 μ m, SGE)

However, this analytical approach did not enable identification of a peak on the chromatogram based on the retention times of these OZ. This may be due to co-elution issues, since oak wood is a complex matrix, or it could be related to detection and sensitivity issues. A semi-preparative HPLC fractionation was therefore performed. Similar fractions were gathered and analysed by GC-O-TOFMS. Both OZ were detected in the same gathered fractions (F3) (Table 2).

Table 2: GC-O analysis on gathered fractions (F3) of different toasted oak wood extracts (Vanilla, Toasted and Smoked).

LRI		Sensory descriptors (N=4)			Odorous zones
BP20	DB5	Vanilla	Toasted	Smoked	
1839	1278	puff pastry, cereal	puff pastry, cereal	-	OZ1
1928	1392	puff pastry, cereal	puff pastry, cereal	-	OZ1'
1953	1453	metallic (fatty, butter)	metallic (fatty, butter)	metallic (fatty, butter)	OZ2

One compound, 2,4,6-nonatrienal, was suggested for association with OZ1 based on similar LRI on polar and non-polar columns and sensory descriptors similar to those cited in the literature. Schuh and Schieberle [8] identified this compound as the key odorant in oat flakes, with an oatmeal-like and sweet odour. Since the standard is not commercially available, organic synthesis was performed (Figure 1).

The organic synthesis resulted in the formation of a mixture of four isomers of 2,4,6-nonatrienal, with two major compounds in a 6:4 ratio corresponding to the E,E,Z and E,E,E isomers, respectively, according to GC-MS and ¹H NMR analysis. Isomerization occurred during the second Wittig reaction. In fact, based on ¹H NMR data, there were two compounds for methyl-2,4,6-nonatrienoate, which is an intermediate product of the reaction. J_{6-7} coupling constant revealed a *trans* configuration (14.85 Hz) and a *cis* configuration (11.1 Hz) at the double bonds at C-6. Furthermore, specific multiplicity profiles were observed between E,E,E and E,E,Z isomers. 2,4,6-nonatrienal showed the same constants and multiplicity profiles, which allowed for well-characterized isomers.

Figure 1: Synthetic route used in the synthesis of *(E,E,Z)*-2,4,6-nonatrienal. (DMP: Dess-Martin periodinane; DIBAL: diisobutylaluminium hydride).

Semi-preparative HPLC purification was performed to isolate each isomer and *(E,E,Z)*-2,4,6-nonatrienal was obtained with 99 % purity. The compound was co-injected with an oak wood extract to confirm its identification using GC-O-TOF MS (Figure 2A).

In addition, the characteristic odour of OZ1' led to identify 2,4,6-decatrienal as responsible of this OZ. In fact, in literature this compound is also described in oat with an oat-like odour [9]. Moreover, its LRI on polar (1984) and non-polar (1376) correspond to our [9,10]. As 2,4,6-nonatrienal, this compound present different isomers, but the *(E,E,Z)* and *(E,E,E)*-2,4,6-decatrienal are the most abundant.

Figure 2: GC-MS NCI analysis of oak wood extract with (black) and without (orange) standard: synthesised 2,4,6-nonatrienal isomers (A) and *(E)*-4,5-epoxy-*(E)*-2-decenal (B). ($m/z=136$ and $m/z=97$, respectively).

Regarding OZ2, its specific odour enabled identification of *(E)*-4,5-epoxy-*(E)*-2-decenal, which was confirmed by its LRI, mass spectrum and the injection of its standard (Figure 2B). In the literature, studies have shown that *(E)*-4,5-epoxy-*(E)*-alk-2-enals are responsible for this characteristic metallic odour [11,12], particularly the *(E)*-4,5-epoxy-*(E)*-2-decenal which is the most odorant of these compounds.

These compounds were identified in oak wood for oenological use for the first time.

Distribution of 2,4,6-nonatrienal isomers and trans-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal during toasting

Quantitation experiments were conducted using oak wood samples heated with different time and temperature combinations to understand the formation of these two new compounds. Different species were also studied (sessile, pedunculate, American, Caucase). This study detected 2,4,6-nonatrienal in non-toasted oak woods. Optimum treatment was achieved with medium heating (180°C for 30 min) and, in general, high temperatures were not conducive to the formation of the *E,E,Z* isomer (Figure 3). On the other hand, toasting was conducive to the formation of the *E,E,E* isomer (Figure 3), except in extreme conditions (240 °C for 30 min). These observations were consistent with the sensory perceptions. The expert panel described the lightly toasted oak wood samples as having brioche, pastry and sweet notes, which were not cited in the descriptions of highly toasted oak wood.

High temperatures are conducive to the formation of *(E)*-4,5-epoxy-*(E)*-2-decenal (Figure 4). It was present in non-toasted oak wood, but in small amounts compared to the other conditions, in which it can reach ten times its initial concentration.

Figure 3: Distribution of (E,E,Z) and (E,E,E)-2,4,6-nonatrienal during temperature increases with the same heating time: 10 min (A) or 30 min (B). (n=3; Different letters correspond to significant differences according to one way ANOVA at p-value<0.05).

Figure 4: Distribution of (E)-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal during temperature increases with the same heating time: 10 min (A) or 30 min (B). (n=3; Different letters correspond to significant differences according to one way ANOVA at p-value<0.05).

Fatty acids, specifically linoleic and linolenic acids, had already been described in oat, butterfat and beans as precursors of (E)-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal and 2,4,6-nonatrienal, respectively [8, 11, 13, 14] based on an oxidation mechanism. It is therefore likely that, in our experimental conditions, the association between heat stress and oxidative stress caused fatty acid degradation and aldehyde production, and, depending on the chemical structure of the compounds, their degradation or volatilization at higher temperatures.

Impact of 2,4,6-nonatrienal and trans-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal on the aromas of wines and spirits

The two isomers of 2,4,6-nonatrienal were identified in red wine and quantitated. Concentrations of the most odorous isomer were generally higher (441.3 ng/L) than concentrations of the E,E,E isomer (178.2 ng/L) (Table 3). However, in some red wines, only the E,E,E isomer was present. Moreover, 2,4,6-nonatrienal is not exclusively present in red wines aged in barrels. Quantitation revealed that 2,4,6-nonatrienal can also be present in red wines not aged in barrels (Table 3). However, concentrations in red wines aged in barrels are higher (441.32 ng/L) than those observed in red wines not aged in barrels (275.84 ng/L). These observations led to the conclusion that this compound can be released through contact with oak wood and/or produced during grape ripening or winemaking. In the case of (E)-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal, its distribution differs from one wine to another. First, concentrations are higher in red wines not aged in barrels (24.3 ng/L in average). Furthermore, few red wines aged in barrels contain (E)-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal, but concentrations of this compound can reach 56.3 ng/L (66.7 ng/L) in red wines not aged in barrels. Like 2,4,6-nonatrienal, (E)-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal can be released through contact with oak wood and/or during grape ripening and winemaking.

When we compare the results obtained for the two new compounds in red wines, we observe a noticeable difference in their distribution. They are not necessarily present in the same samples.

Table 3: Distribution (ng/L) of (E,E,Z)-2,4,6-nonatrienal (1), (E,E,E)-2,4,6-nonatrienal (2) and (E)-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal (3) in several red wines aged (OB) or not (NOB) in oak barrels. (n= number of samples, SD=standard deviation, Q1=quartile 1 and Q3=quartile 3).

Compounds		n	Average	SD	Median	Min.	Max.	Q1	Q3
(1)	OB	11	146.5	160.1	80.4	3.6	441.3	32.3	254.2
	N-OB	24	88.5	72.7	64.0	12.3	275.8	44.1	115.6
(2)	OB	17	54.4	55.1	47.3	2.7	169.6	10.7	66.7
	N-OB	37	59.0	38.8	44.9	10.9	178.2	29.6	79.5
(3)	OB	5	22.7	19.4	17.3	6.4	56.3	14.0	19.4
	N-OB	37	24.3	10.3	23.4	8.5	66.7	18.2	27.6

To determine their organoleptic impact, ODT were evaluated by experts. The ODT of *trans*-4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-decenal was evaluated at 43 ng/L in model wine solution (n=17). The ODT of (E,E,Z)-2,4,6-nonatrienal was evaluated at 16 ng/L in model wine solution (n=10). Both have a very low ODT and are among the most odorous compounds found in wines. Based on its concentrations in red wine, which are much higher than its individual ODT, (E,E,Z)-2,4,6-nonatrienal directly affects the aroma of red wine. (E)-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal, on the other hand, affects the aroma of certain red wines.

Conclusion

Oak wood barrels have been known and used for many years, but some of the volatile compounds responsible for their aromas remain unknown. In this study, two new compounds were identified and characterized: 2,4,6-nonatrienal and (E)-4,5-epoxy-(E)-2-decenal. They are responsible for puff pastry and metallic odours, respectively. Quantitation in oak wood revealed the influence of toasting intensity on their formation. In red wines, both have a direct organoleptic impact on the aroma due to their low ODT. Additional sensory analysis will be needed to determine how they modulate the aroma of wine and spirits. Quantitation in other wines (red and white) and spirits is currently underway. The initial results reveal the presence of 2,4,6-nonatrienal in some spirits.

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